

diversity revolution

checklist

Tools for assessing the
respecting diversity at
the level of organizational
culture, climate and staff
competencies

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DIVERSITY REVOLUTION CHECKLIST

Tools for assessing the respecting diversity at the level of organizational culture, climate and staff competencies

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The publication was created within the project

DIVERSITY REVOLUTION: From value to practice

Cover page designed by: Anica Novak
Design of the publication: Anica Novak

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

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Technical instructions for using the checklist "diversity revolution"

Organizations/institutions working with young people should structure their work in a way that best addresses the needs of the users, respects their diversities, and utilizes them as a starting point — acknowledging the strengths of young individuals. Furthermore, they should integrate the value of diversity into all elements of their functioning. With the idea of facilitating the assessment of their operation concerning diversity appreciation in practice for management and employees in diverse institutions/organizations, the project team "Diversity Revolution," led by researchers from the Institute for Educational Research in Belgrade and CEPORA – Center for Positive Youth Development, has created the Checklist "Diversity Revolution".

Introduction: basic theoretical assumptions

Living in contemporary society involves frequent intercultural experiences, meaning interactions with individuals belonging to different cultural groups. Therefore, the need for each individual to prepare for a competent life and functioning in a multicultural and intercultural world becomes an essential aspect of the functioning of institutions/organizations on a global level. To successfully provide services to all people, institutions/organizations need to develop standards, policies, and practices within appropriate cultural frameworks that will adequately address the needs of different individuals. Diversity is highlighted as a crucial value, especially in institutions/organizations directly working or coming into contact with children and youth, such as institutions/organizations within the educational system, social welfare, or youth work. However, despite interest and dedication to equality, diversity, and inclusion, significant variations still exist in how institutions/organizations define, understand, and respond to issues related to these constructs.

Professional and scientific literature abound with insights into the significance of respecting diversity, the essential elements for fostering diversity, and tools for assessing respecting diversity in institutions/organizations working with children and youth. The concept of "diversity" is interpreted and operationalized in various ways. In the broadest sense, diversity is described as the presence of individual differences that are inherent and/or acquired through socialization, such as race, national-ethnic-cultural origin, gender, age, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, disability, religion, education, values, family/marital status, etc. Diversity is typically associated with someone's cultural affiliation. In this text, the terms "culture" and "cultural diversity" imply not only culture related to race, ethnic origin, and ancestry but also the culture shared by people with certain common characteristics – beliefs, shared experiences, ideals, patterns of social and interpersonal relationships, ways of perception, thinking, and behavior, and, in general, lifestyle.

For respecting diversity to successfully transition from an axiological framework into the practical work of an institution/organization, numerous elements of the institution's/organization's functioning and its actors are crucial. These elements are recognized at the level of the institution's/organization's culture, the interrelationships among all staff members, as well as between staff and the users they work with (organizational climate). Additionally, individual capacities and resources of leaders and staff to perceive diversity as a value and to respond adequately to it (cultural competencies) play a significant role. Culture and climate in an institution/organization are two alternative constructs that conceptualize the ways in which people perceive and describe their work environment.

Culture of an institution/organization determines the proper way of behaving within it. It consists of shared beliefs and values established by leaders, which are then communicated and emphasized within the institution/organization, ultimately shaping the perception, understanding, and behavior of the employees. The fundamental elements of the culture of an institution/organization include a shared sense of purpose and vision, norms, values, beliefs, and assumptions, as well as rituals, traditions, ceremonies, architecture, artifacts, and symbols. When these elements of culture within an institution/organization are inconsistent or incongruent, things will not function properly.

Climate in an institution/organization refers to the atmosphere, emotional tone, general mood or "vibration" within the institution/organization. The climate in an institution/organization consists of recurring patterns of behavior, attitudes, and feelings that characterize life in an institution/organization, as well as perceptions and meanings attached to policies, practices, and procedures in an institution/organization. The main characteristics of an ideal working climate are: inclusiveness and belonging; diversity; respect; physical, emotional and psychological safety; openness and freedom to express oneself, ask questions, take risks and make mistakes without judgment; adequate mentoring to encourage learning and career development.

Cultural competencies are defined as a set of values, attitudes, skills, and knowledge necessary for understanding and respecting culturally diverse individuals. They constitute the foundation for effective and appropriate interaction and communication, key to establishing positive and constructive intercultural relations. Cultural competence implies that a person is comfortable in the company of those who do not belong to their cultural group, possesses knowledge about their own and other cultural groups, and has the ability to engage in positive interactions with people of different cultural characteristics. According to one of the most commonly used models, cultural competencies consist of three components: awareness, knowledge, and skills. Cultural awareness pertains to the individual's appropriate and suitable attitudes, beliefs, and assumptions about different cultures. Cultural awareness essentially involves continuous reflection on one's attitudes towards other cultures and how one's own culture influences the formation of those attitudes. Cultural knowledge reflects understanding of one's own culture and other cultures, including cultural norms, while cultural skills relate to the ability to engage in effective and unbiased interaction with individuals from different cultures.

About the checklist “diversity revolution”

The checklist "Diversity Revolution" is based on contemporary and relevant theoretical knowledge about key elements of respecting diversity in institutions/organizations working with children and youth. These elements are identified within the domains of the institution's/organization's culture and climate, as well as the individual cultural competencies of management and staff. After reviewing the theoretical foundations of respecting diversity, a survey of existing tools for assessing respecting diversity (questionnaires, interview protocols, checklists, scales) at all levels of the institution's/organization's functioning (culture, climate, individual competencies of the institution's/organization's actors) working with children and youth in the educational system, social welfare, and youth work was conducted. The content of the checklist is designed based on the review, analysis, integration, and adaptation of a total of 43 different tools for assessing diversity appreciation (detailed in the next chapter).

After the initial development of the checklist, it was piloted in three countries (Serbia, Italy, Slovenia). Cultural universality testing of the checklist, as well as testing of the items themselves, was conducted in each country. The sample in each country included leaders and employees from three sectors – youth work, education, and social work. The final checklist was created based on feedback obtained through the pilot process.

The checklist "Diversity Revolution" is created with the intention of serving as a respecting diversity screening tool in all domains of the functioning of an institution/organization – the domain of culture, the domain of climate, and the domain of individual cultural competencies of the actors – both management and staff. Two versions of the checklist have been formulated – one for management and one for employees. The checklist for management comprises a total of 33 items (11 items for each of the three domains – culture, climate, and cultural competencies), while the checklist for employees includes 35 items (11 items for the culture domain, 13 items for the climate domain, and 11 items for the cultural competencies domain). At the end of the checklist, in both versions, management and employees are provided the opportunity to write up three things that need and can be done to improve diversity appreciation in the institution/organization - in other words, to propose priorities for improvement.

Screening and assessment of respecting diversity in the institution/organization may include three steps, that is, three levels of assessment:

- 1.** The first level of assessment of respecting diversity in the institution/organization involves the completion of a checklist by the management (for example, director, acting director, deputy director, secretary, lawyer). Based on the first step of the assessment, the management has the opportunity to gain insight into the positive practice of respect for diversity in the institution/organization, but it can also map certain omissions and room for improvement, which further opens up space for planning specific interventions to improve respect for diversity in its institution/organization. If it is estimated that it is necessary to get a more "objective" and comprehensive picture of respect for diversity in the institution/organization, the management can proceed to the second step of the assessment.

2. The second level of assessment involves the distribution of a checklist to all employees in the institution/organization, in order to see their perception of respecting diversity in different domains of functioning. In this way, the management can gain insight into the employees' observations, which can be similar, but also completely opposite to the management's observation, which opens up space for new constructive discussions and improvement of the functioning of the institution/organization.
3. The third level of assessment serves a detailed and in-depth assessment of one or both domains of institutional functioning (culture and/or climate) or a detailed assessment of individual cultural competencies of management and/or employees. After performing a quick screening using the checklist and getting a preliminary insight into the functioning of their institution/organization in terms of fostering diversity, in the third, final, assessment step, management and/or employees are provided with a list of 43 tools to assess the fostering diversity in the institution/organization (at all levels of functioning). Management and employees can, from the created list of 43 tools for assessing respecting diversity, choose the one that best suits them considering the described characteristics of the assessment tool (type of assessment tool – checklist, questionnaire, scale; domain of functioning that it assesses – culture, climate and/or cultural competences; sector – education, social protection and/or youth work; target group for which the instrument is intended; number of items), and to access the selected tool and gain a detailed insight into the level of respect for diversity in the specific domain of functioning (institutional and/or individual). A list of tools suitable for culture/climate/competency assessment is available in the third chapter of the publication.

Checklist “diversity revolution“: version for management

- ✓ The checklist "Diversity Revolution" is used to assess respecting diversity in institutions/organizations working with children and youth, specifically in the domain of organizational culture, interpersonal relationships both among employees and between leadership and employees (organizational climate), and in the domain of individual capacities and resources of management members to perceive diversity among employees as a value and to respond adequately (cultural competencies).
- ✓ The checklist is intended for all members of the institution's/organization's leadership (director, acting director, deputy director, secretary, lawyer, etc.).
- ✓ This is not a test. The goal of the checklist is to help you recognize strengths, as well as weaknesses, or areas that you and your institution/organization can improve to more effectively meet the needs of employees and users belonging to different cultural groups.
- ✓ The questions are divided into three areas: the culture of the institution/organization, the climate of the institution/organization, and cultural competencies. Read each statement and mark the answer that most closely reflects your opinion (YES or NO).
- ✓ At the end of the checklist, you have the opportunity to write up to three things that you believe need and can be changed to enhance respecting diversity in the institution/organization.

Culture of the institution/organization

The fundamental elements of the institution/organization's culture include: a shared sense of purpose, vision, and mission; policies, procedures, and practices; norms, values, beliefs, and assumptions; rituals, traditions, and ceremonies; architecture, artifacts, and symbols.

Imagine your institution/organization and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

	In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
1.	Vision and mission are defined to encompass the appreciation of diversity.		
2.	The significance of respecting diversity of employees and users is clearly emphasized in internal documents (policies) and procedures.		

3.	In the case of discrimination against employees and users, responses align with established rules and procedures.		
4.	When assessing the needs of all employees (e.g., breaks, holidays, meals, traditions), their individual characteristics (e.g., ethnic background, race, religion, gender, language, age, etc.) are taken into account.		
5.	Leadership considers the cultural beliefs, strengths, and vulnerabilities of all employees when making decisions and assigning tasks.		
6.	All employees can rely on mentorship or other forms of support.		
7.	All employees are praised for a job well done.		
8.	Leadership takes care of the well-being of all employees.		
9.	Leadership encourages participation, promotes diversity, and establishes measures to ensure equal opportunities for everyone.		
10.	Images, posters, artworks, and/or other decorative items reflect the diverse cultures of employees and users.		
11.	Magazines, brochures, literature, and other materials reflect the diverse cultures of employees and users.		

Climate in the institution/organization

The organizational climate refers to the atmosphere, emotional tone, overall mood, or "vibration" within the institution/organization. The main characteristics of the climate include: respect; open communication and collaboration; safety; adequate mentorship to encourage learning and career development; perceptions and meanings attributed to policies, practices, and procedures.

Imagine your institution/organization and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

	In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
12.	All employees are valued and respected (e.g., all employees are respected regardless of gender, sexual orientation, ethnic background, disability; the privacy of employees is respected; employees are addressed by the names they prefer, etc.).		

13.	Attention is given to significant events in the lives of all employees (e.g., the birth of a child, birthdays, weddings, bereavement).		
14.	There is good communication among all employees (e.g., constructive discussions are held, offensive words are not used, etc.).		
15.	A collaborative atmosphere is present (e.g., constructive dialogues take place, employees advise or assist each other in skill development, responsiveness to different ideas, etc.).		
16.	Achievements of all employees are valued (e.g., all employees are praised for a job well done).		
17.	Employees behave in a friendly manner towards each other.		
18.	Employees function as a good team.		
19.	Professional development of all employees is encouraged.		
20.	Bullying is absent.		
21.	All employees are familiar with anti-discrimination policies and procedures.		
22.	Policies and procedures are consistently and fairly applied to all employees.		

Cultural competence

Cultural competences include adequate and appropriate attitudes, opinions and assumptions about different cultures; understanding of own and other cultures and cultural norms; as well as the ability to effectively and impartially communicate and interact with culturally diverse individuals.

Imagine your employees, recall interactions with them, and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

	In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
23.	I have a positive view of employee diversity and believe that diversity should be celebrated.		
24.	I am able to recognize my stereotypes when interacting with employees and have developed strategies to mitigate the harm caused by these stereotypes.		
25.	I can empathize with the feelings, thoughts, and behaviors of employees from different cultural groups.		

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26.	I have an open and unbiased attitude towards all employees.		
27.	I can acknowledge that my knowledge about certain cultural characteristics of employees is limited and strive to create opportunities to learn more.		
28.	I understand that individual differences among employees are important parts of their identity that they value, and I appreciate them as well.		
29.	I understand the role and impact of culture on the experiences and behavior of employees.		
30.	I can successfully respond when I observe discriminatory behavior towards any employee.		
31.	I communicate effectively and respectfully with all employees.		
32.	I can recognize my own biases in a specific situation and not react based on them.		
33.	I make an effort to professionally develop and train in the "best" practices to enhance knowledge and skills for working with employees from different cultures.		

In relation to the mapped strengths and challenges, select up to 3 things that you consider to be priorities - on which it is necessary and possible (in accordance with available resources) to work in the following period:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Checklist “diversity revolution“: version for employees

- ✓ The checklist "Diversity Revolution" is designed to assess the appreciation of diversity in institutions/organizations working with children and youth. It covers the domain of organizational culture, interpersonal relationships among employees, as well as interactions between employees and the users they work with (organizational climate). It also addresses the individual capacities and resources of employees to perceive diversity among the users as a value and to react appropriately (cultural competencies).
- ✓ The checklist is intended for all employees within an institution/organization, as well as for volunteers. It is meant for anyone engaged with the institution/organization, familiar with its functioning, but not necessarily in a formal employment relationship.
- ✓ This is not a test. The goal of the checklist is to help you recognize strengths, as well as weaknesses, or areas that you and your institution/organization can improve to more effectively meet the needs of employees and users belonging to different cultural groups.
- ✓ The questions are divided into three areas: the culture of the institution/organization, the climate of the institution/organization, and cultural competencies. Read each statement and mark the answer that most closely reflects your opinion (YES or NO).
- ✓ At the end of the checklist, you have the opportunity to write up to three things that you believe need and can be changed to enhance respecting diversity in the institution/organization.

Culture of the institution/organization

The fundamental elements of the institution/organization's culture include: a shared sense of purpose, vision, and mission; policies, procedures, and practices; norms, values, beliefs, and assumptions; rituals, traditions, and ceremonies; architecture, artifacts, and symbols.

Imagine your institution/organization and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

	In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
1.	Vision and mission are defined to encompass the appreciation of diversity.		

2.	The importance of respecting the diversity of employees and users is clearly emphasized in internal documents (policies) and procedures.		
3.	In the case of discrimination, actions are taken in accordance with established rules and procedures.		
4.	When assessing the needs of all employees (e.g., breaks, holidays, meals, traditions), their individual characteristics are taken into account (e.g., ethnic background, race, religion, gender, language, age, etc.).		
5.	Leadership considers the cultural beliefs, strengths, and vulnerabilities of all employees when making decisions and assigning tasks.		
6.	All employees can rely on mentoring or other types of support.		
7.	All employees are praised for a job well done.		
8.	Leadership takes care of the well-being of all employees.		
9.	Leadership encourages participation, promotes diversity, and establishes measures to ensure equal opportunities for everyone.		
10.	Pictures, posters, artworks, and/or other decorative items reflect the diverse cultures of employees and users.		
11.	Magazines, brochures, literature, and other materials reflect the diverse cultures of employees and users.		

Climate in the institution/organization

The organizational climate refers to the atmosphere, emotional tone, overall mood, or "vibration" within the institution/organization. The main characteristics of the climate include: respect; open communication and collaboration; safety; adequate mentorship to encourage learning and career development; perceptions and meanings attributed to policies, practices, and procedures.

Imagine your institution/organization and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

	In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
12.	Leadership treats all employees with respect (e.g., all employees are respected regardless of gender, sexual orientation, ethnic background, disability; the privacy of employees is respected; employees are addressed by the names they wish to be called, etc.).		

13.	All employees respect each other (e.g., all employees are respected regardless of gender, sexual orientation, ethnic background, disability; the privacy of employees is respected; employees are addressed by the names they wish to be called, etc.).		
14.	Attention is given to significant events of all employees (e.g., childbirth, birthday, wedding, death in the family).		
15.	There is good communication between leadership and employees (e.g., constructive discussions are held, offensive words are not used, etc.).		
16.	There is good communication among all employees (e.g., constructive discussions are held, offensive words are not used, etc.).		
17.	There is a climate of collaboration (e.g., constructive dialogues are held, employees advise each other or help each other develop skills, there is responsiveness to different ideas, etc.).		
18.	Achievements of all employees are valued (e.g., all employees are praised for successfully completing their tasks).		
19.	Employees behave in a friendly manner toward each other.		
20.	Employees function as a good team.		
21.	Professional development of all employees is encouraged.		
22.	Bullying is present.		
23.	All employees are familiar with antidiscrimination policies and procedures.		
24.	Policies and procedures are consistently and fairly applied to all employees.		

Cultural competence

Cultural competences include adequate and appropriate attitudes, opinions and assumptions about different cultures; understanding of own and other cultures and cultural norms; as well as the ability to effectively and impartially communicate and interact with culturally diverse individuals.

Imagine your employees, recall interactions with them, and circle the answer that most closely reflects your opinion.

In our institution/organization...	YES	NO
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25.	I have a positive view of the diversity of users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate, and I believe that diversity should be celebrated.		
26.	I am aware of my stereotypes in interactions with users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate, and I have developed strategies to mitigate the harm caused by these stereotypes.		
27.	I can empathize with the feelings, thoughts, and behaviors of users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate, who belong to different cultural groups.		
28.	I have an open and unbiased attitude towards users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate.		
29.	I can recognize that my knowledge of certain cultural characteristics of users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate is limited, and I strive to create opportunities to learn more.		
30.	I know that the individual differences of users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate are important parts of their identity, which they value, and I appreciate them as well.		
31.	I understand the role and impact of culture on the experiences and behavior of users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate.		
32.	I can successfully respond when I observe discriminatory behavior towards any user and/or colleague with whom I closely collaborate.		
33.	I communicate effectively and with respect with all users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate.		
34.	I can recognize my own biases in a specific situation and refrain from reacting based on them.		
35.	I strive for professional development and training in “best practices” to enhance knowledge and skills for working with users and/or colleagues with whom I closely collaborate from different cultural groups.		

In relation to the mapped strengths and challenges, select up to 3 things that you consider to be priorities - on which it is necessary and possible (in accordance with available resources) to work in the following period:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

List of tools for assessing respectation diversity in institutions/organizations

After reviewing contemporary knowledge and based on defined minimum standards for diversity appreciation, the review of existing tools for assessing diversity appreciation (questionnaires, interview protocols, checklists, scales) at all levels of the institution's/organization's functioning (culture, climate, individual competencies of the institution's/organization's employees) that work with children and youth within the educational system, social protection, and youth work has been initiated.

The general conclusion is that there is a large number of diverse tools for assessing respecting diversity in institutions/organizations working with children and youth. For the purposes of this project and publication, a list of 43 different tools for assessing diversity appreciation at the institutional level (culture and climate) or individual level (cultural competencies) has been created, which we assessed could be useful for an in-depth assessment of diversity appreciation in one of the mentioned domains. The most represented instruments are those focused on assessing individual cultural competencies.

Each tool is briefly presented through the following indicators:

- ✓ Tool type (checklist/questionnaire/scale);
- ✓ The functioning domain it assesses (culture/climate/competencies);
- ✓ The sector in which it can be applied (education/social protection/youth work);
- ✓ The target group for which the tool is intended (youth/adults);
- ✓ The number of items;
- ✓ Brief description of what it assesses. Interested individuals can choose the tool that best suits their needs based on its characteristics;
- ✓ The source or reference where the selected tools can be found is initially indicated in parentheses next to the tool's name and then listed in the bibliography.

For a quick overview of the presented assessment tools, refer to the Appendix at the end of this chapter.

1

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Administrator cultural competence self-assessment

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: social work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 59

DESCRIPTION: The scale serves to measure the social workers competencies by assessing their: knowledge of community; personal involvement; resources and linkages; staffing; organizational policy and procedure; reaching out to communities.

REFERENCE: Minneapolis Public Educations. Positive Education Climate Tool Kit. Available at: <https://www.coursehero.com/file/plgav5h/Minneapolis-Public-Schools-Positive-School-Climate-Tool-Kit-First-Edition-108/>

2

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Adults tolerance questionnaire

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 38

DESCRIPTION: The scale is focused on how to: 1. adopt a social-emotional lens, 2. know the students and continually develop cultural responsiveness, 3. move the discipline paradigm from “punishment” to “opportunities to teach desired behavior,” and 4. resist the criminalization of school behavior.

REFERENCE: Blitz, L.V., Yull, D., & Clauhs, M. (2020). Bringing sanctuary to education: Assessing education climate as a foundation for culturally responsive trauma-informed approaches for urban educations. *Urban Education*, 55(1), 95-124.

3

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Adults' perception of cultural competence

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults, young people

No. of items: 25

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures three basic cultural competencies in education: awareness, knowledge and skills.

REFERENCE: Leighton, L. (2010). Adults' perceptions of their cultural competencies: An investigation in the relationships among teacher characteristics and cultural competence (Doctoral dissertation). Mount Saint Vincent University.

4

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Assessment of cultural competences

TYPE: Yes/no

AREA: culture, climate, competencies

SECTOR: social work, youth work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 45

DESCRIPTION: The purpose of the instrument is to assist organizations to assess their progress towards cultural competence, both at the organizational and individual level. The instrument consists of three sections: 1) Assessment of Organizational Cultural Competence, 2) Respondent Information, and 3) Assessment of Individual Cultural Competence.

REFERENCE: AUCD Multicultural Council. (2004) Instructions for Assessment of Organizational Cultural Competence. AUCD Multicultural Council.

5

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

California brief multicultural competence Scale

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 21

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures individual, self-reported multi-cultural competency and training needs in the following four areas: multicultural knowledge; awareness of cultural barriers; sensitivity and responsiveness to consumers; and socio-cultural diversities.

REFERENCE: Gamst, G., Dana, R. H., Der-Karabetian, A., Aragon, M., Arellano, L., Morrow, G., & Martenson, L. (2004). Cultural Competency Revised: The California Brief Multicultural Competence Scale. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counseling and Development*, 37(3), 163-183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07481756.2004.11909758>

6

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Color-blind racial attitudes scale

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 20

DESCRIPTION: The scale focuses on cultural competences related to race by measuring: 1. unawareness of racial privilege; 2. unawareness of institutional discrimination and 3. unawareness to blatant racial issues.

REFERENCE: Neville, H. A., Lilly, R. L., Duran, G., Lee, R. M., & Browne, L. (2000). Construction and initial validation of the color-blind racial attitudes scale (CoBRAS). *Journal of counseling psychology*, 47(1), 59-70. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-0167.47.1.59>

7

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Core cultural competencies

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: youth work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 64

DESCRIPTION: Bearing in mind that cultural competency is one of the key competencies of youth work, using this scale, respondents rank different competencies related to equity, access and opportunity.

REFERENCE: Stone, B, & Rennekamp, R. (2004) New Foundations for the 4-H Youth Development Profession: 4-H Professional Research, Knowledge, and Competencies Study. https://4-hhistorypreservation.com/eMedia/eOneTimeReports/New_Foundations.pdf

8

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Critical cultural competence in social work supervision

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: social work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 18

DESCRIPTION: The survey is designed to assess social workers' views of culturally competent leadership and to identify their experiences with their supervisors. Domains include demographics, questions about the supervisor's knowledge and appreciation of other cultures, and questions on specific examples of culturally competent and incompetent behaviors.

REFERENCE: Lusk, M., Terrazas, S., & Salcido, R. (2017). Critical cultural competence in social work supervision. Human Service Organizations: Management, Leadership & Governance, 41(5), 464-476. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23303131.2017.1313801>

9

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Cultural and linguistic competence policy assessment

TYPE: Mixed questions

AREA: culture, climate, competencies

SECTOR: social work, youth work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 51

DESCRIPTION: Knowledge, organizational philosophy, personal involvement, resources and linkages and human resources are addressed in this instrument for measuring the cultural and linguistic competencies of social or youth workers.

REFERENCE: Assessment, L. C. P. Cultural and Linguistic Competence Policy Assessment. http://archive.mhsoac.ca.gov/Meetings/PriorMeetings_2014/docs/Meetings/2014/April/CLCC_041614_Tab4_CLCPolicyAssessment.pdf

10

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Cultural competence self-assessment

TYPE: Mixed questions

AREA: culture, climate, competencies

SECTOR: social work (health care)

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 122

DESCRIPTION: This self-assessment tool could serve social workers to assess their cultural competences by addressing: ethnic/cultural characteristics; organizational approaches to accommodating diversity needs and attributes and organizational links to patients and the communities they serve.

REFERENCE: Andrulis, D. P., Delbanco, T., Avakian, L., & Shaw-Taylor, Y. (2004). Conducting a cultural competence self-assessment. *Management Sciences for Health*.

11

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Cultural competence self-assessment checklist

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 36

DESCRIPTION: This self-assessment tool is designed to explore individual cultural competence. Its purpose is to help respondents to consider their skills, knowledge, and awareness of themselves in their interactions with others. Its goal is to assist them to recognize what they can do to become more effective in working and living in a diverse environment.

REFERENCE: Diversity Committee (2018). Diversity Self-Assessment. <https://www.washcoll.edu/campus-community/diversity-equity-and-inclusion/Diversity%20Self-Assessment.pdf>

12

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Cultural competence self-assessment questionnaire

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: social work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 79

DESCRIPTION: The scale is designed to assist service agencies working with children with disabilities and their families in self-evaluation of their cross-cultural competence (attitude, practice, policy, and structure).

REFERENCE: Mason, J. L. (1995). Cultural Competence Self-Assessment Questionnaire: A Manual for Users. Portland State University: Research and Training Center on Family Support and Children's Mental Health. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED399684.pdf>

13

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Cultural proficiency continuum Q-Sort

TYPE: Q-sort

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 30

DESCRIPTION: The scale is focused on measuring cultural competences addressing the following: cultural destructiveness; cultural incapacity; cultural blindness; cultural precompetence; cultural competence; cultural proficiency.

REFERENCE: Cormier, D. R. (2021). Assessing preservice adults' cultural competence with the cultural proficiency continuum Q-sort. *Educational Researcher*, 50(1), 17-29. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X20936670>

14

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Diversity climate scale

TYPE: 6-point scale

AREA: climate

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 30

DESCRIPTION: The scale serves to evaluate an organization's diversity and inclusion climate.

REFERENCE: Yeats, L. F. (2018). Organizational assessment of diversity and inclusion (Doctoral dissertation, Pepperdine University). <https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2003&context=etd> (p. 62)

15

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Diversity management questionnaire

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 3

DESCRIPTION: The extent to which a culture of diversity exists in an organization is reflected by responses to three survey questions.

REFERENCE: Pitts, D.W. (2009). Diversity management, job satisfaction, and performance: Evidence from U.S. Federal Agencies. *Public Administration Review*, 69(2), 328-338.

16

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Diversity perceptions scale

TYPE: 6 – point scale

AREA: climate, competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 16

DESCRIPTION: The instrument consists of two sections - Organizational and Individual. The purpose of the instrument is to assess perceptions of organizational fairness and organizational inclusion together with self-perceptions towards personal diversity values and personal comfort.

REFERENCE: Mor Barak, M.E., Cherin, D.A., & Berkman, S. (1998). Organizational and personal dimensions in diversity climate: ethnic and gender differences in employee perceptions, *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 34(1), 82-104.

17

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Education climate for diversity - Secondary scale

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: young people

No. of items: 39

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures: equal status; quality of interaction, frequency of interaction; support for positive interaction; cultural socialization; promotion of cultural competence; critical consciousness; stereotyping; mainstream socialization; colorblind socialization.

REFERENCE: Byrd, C. M. (2019). A measure of education racial socialization and quality of intergroup interactions. *Cultural Diversity and Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 25(2), 1-15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/cdp0000202>

18

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Education climate survey – staff

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 17

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures the school climate via: connectedness, safety, academic emphasis and parental involvement.

REFERENCE: Ramsey, C. M., Spira, A. P., Parisi, J. M., & Rebok, G. W. (2016). Education climate: Perceptual differences between young people, parents, and education staff. *Education effectiveness and education improvement*, 27(4), 629-641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2016.1199436>

19

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Education climate survey – young people in grade 3 to 5

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: young people

No. of items: 17

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures the school climate via: connectedness, safety, academic emphasis and parental involvement.

REFERENCE: Ramsey, C. M., Spira, A. P., Parisi, J. M., & Rebok, G. W. (2016). Education climate: Perceptual differences between young people, parents, and education staff. *Education effectiveness and education improvement*, 27(4), 629-641. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2016.1199436>

20

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Education-wide cultural competence observation checklist

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: culture, climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 33

DESCRIPTION: The scale measure culture and climate through: school vision/mission, curriculum, student interaction and leadership, teachers, teaching and learning, parents and outer community, conflict management, assessments.

REFERENCE: Bustamante, R. B., & Nelson, J. A. (2007). The education-wide cultural competence observation checklist. https://www.greateducationpartnership.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/SCCOC_March_2017.pdf

21

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Ethnic-sensitive inventory

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: social work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 24

DESCRIPTION: This scale is created in order to enhance practitioner skills with ethnic minorities. The questions tackle six treatment phases of client–counselor interaction: precontact, problem identification, problem specification, mutual goal formulation, problem solving and termination.

REFERENCE: Ho, M. K. (1990). Use of ethnic-sensitive inventory (ESI) to enhance practitioner skills with minorities. *Journal of multicultural social work*, 1(1), 57-68. https://doi.org/10.1300/J285v01n01_05

22

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Exploring and assessing intercultural competence

TYPE: Likert scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 43

DESCRIPTION: The instrument addresses the multiple dimensions of intercultural competencies: knowledge, attitudes, skills and awareness.

REFERENCE: Fantini, A. E. (2007). Exploring and assessing intercultural competence. https://digitalcollections.sit.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1001&context=worldlearning_publications/

23

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Inclusive leadership in educations – LEI-Q questionnaire

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 40

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures cultural competencies in education by focusing on the school as an inclusive community; management of the teaching-learning processes and development of teaching professionalism.

REFERENCE: Crisol Moya, E., Molonia, T., & Caurcel Cara, M. J. (2020). Inclusive leadership and education quality: Adaptation and validation of the questionnaire “Inclusive Leadership in Educations” (LEI-Q) to the Italian context. *Sustainability*, 12(13), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12135375>

24

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Index for inclusion

TYPE: 3-point scale

AREA: culture, climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults, young people

No. of items: Varies based on target group

DESCRIPTION: The scale serves to evaluate culture and climate in order to: create inclusive cultures; produce inclusive policies and evolve inclusive practices.

REFERENCE: Booth, T., Ainscow, M., & Kingston, D. (2002). *Index for inclusion: Developing play, learning and participation in early years and childcare*. Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education. https://inee.org/sites/default/files/resources/index_for_Inclusion_Developing_Play%2C_Learning_and_Participation_in_the_Early_Years_and_Childcare.pdf

25

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Intercultural adjustment potential scale

TYPE: 7-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 55

DESCRIPTION: This tool represents the measure that predicts intercultural adjustment potential by measuring: emotion regulation, openness, flexibility and critical thinking.

REFERENCE: Matsumoto, D., LeRoux, J., Ratzlaff, C., Tatani, H., Uchida, H., Kim, C., & Araki, S. (2001). Development and validation of a measure of intercultural adjustment potential in Japanese sojourners: The Intercultural Adjustment Potential Scale (ICAPS). *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 25(5), 483-510.

26

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Intercultural sensitivity inventory

TYPE: Yes/no

AREA: competencies (sensitivity)

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: young people

No. of items: 46

DESCRIPTION: The scale is focused on student's competencies by measuring individualism, collectivism, flexibility and open-mindedness.

REFERENCE: McMurray, A. A. (2007). Measuring intercultural sensitivity of international and domestic college young people: The impact of international travel (Doctoral dissertation). University of Florida.

27

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Intercultural sensitivity scale

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies (sensitivity)

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults, young people

No. of items: 24

DESCRIPTION: The scale serves to measure the intercultural sensitivity by addressing the following: interaction engagement, respect for cultural differences, interaction confidence, interaction enjoyment and interaction attentiveness.

REFERENCE: Hammer, M. R., Bennett, M. J., & Wiseman, R. (2003). Measuring intercultural sensitivity: The intercultural development inventory. *International journal of intercultural relations*, 27(4), 421-443. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767\(03\)00032-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767(03)00032-4)

28

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Miville-Guzman universality-diversity

TYPE: 6-point scale

AREA: culture

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: young people

No. of items: 15

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures students' interest in participating in diverse social and cultural activities – the extent to which students value the impact of diversity on self-understanding and personal growth and students' degree of comfort with diverse individuals.

REFERENCE: Kegel, K., & DeBlaere, C. (2014). Universal-diverse orientation in Asian international young people: Confirmatory factor analysis of the Miville-Guzman Universality-Diversity Scale, Short Form. *Cultural Diversity and Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 20(3), 469-474. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034746>

29

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Mor Barak inclusion-exclusion scale

TYPE: 6-point scale

AREA: culture, climate

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 15

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures the degree to which individuals feel part of critical organizational processes such as access to information, involvement and participation with the organization, and influence in the decision-making process.

REFERENCE: Yeats, L. F. (2018). Organizational assessment of diversity and inclusion (Doctoral dissertation, Pepperdine University). <https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2003&context=etd> (p. 62)

30

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Multicultural awareness, knowledge and skills survey

TYPE: 3-point and 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 60

DESCRIPTION: The instrument was designed to assess the impact of instructional strategies on students' level of multicultural development. It measures knowledge, skills and awareness.

REFERENCE: D'Andrea, M., Daniels, J., & Heck, R. (1991). Evaluating the impact of multicultural counseling training. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 70(1), 143-150. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6676.1991.tb01576.x>

31

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Multicultural competency checklist

TYPE: Check-list (yes/no)

AREA: culture

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 22

DESCRIPTION: The check-list refers to: minority representation; curriculum issues; counseling practice and supervision; research considerations; student and faculty competency evaluation; physical environment.

REFERENCE: Ponterotto, J. G., Alexander, C. M., & Grieger, I. (1995). A multicultural competency checklist for counseling training programs. *Journal of Multicultural Counseling and Development*, 23(1), 11-20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-1912.1995.tb00262.x>

32

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Multicultural counseling inventory

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: social work, youth work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 40

DESCRIPTION: The instrument addresses the multicultural competence by measuring: multicultural counseling skills; multicultural awareness; multicultural counseling knowledge; multicultural counseling relationships.

REFERENCE: Sadowsky, G. R. (1996). 8. The Multicultural Counseling Inventory: Validity And Applications In Multicultural Training. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1012&context=burosbookmulticultural>

33

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Multicultural personality questionnaire

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies (sensitivity)

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults, young people

No. of items: 78 (long), 40 (short)

DESCRIPTION: This multidimensional instrument measures the following elements of cultural competencies: cultural empathy, open-mindedness, social initiative, emotional stability and flexibility.

REFERENCE: Van Der Zee, K. I., & Van Oudenhoven, J. P. (2000). The Multicultural Personality Questionnaire: A multidimensional instrument of multicultural effectiveness. *European journal of personality*, 14(4), 291-309. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-0984\(200007/08\)14:4<291::AID-PER377>3.0.CO;2-6](https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-0984(200007/08)14:4<291::AID-PER377>3.0.CO;2-6)

34

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Multiculturally competent service system assessment guide

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: culture, climate, competencies

SECTOR: social work, youth work

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 45

DESCRIPTION: This is a tool for assessing the organization related to multicultural competencies in the following fields: agency demographics, policies, procedures and governance, service/programs, care management, continuity of care, human resources development, quality monitoring and improvement, information/management system. Based on this assessment the organization should formulate culturally competent plan.

REFERENCE: The Connecticut Department of Mental Health and Addiction Services Office of Multicultural Affairs. (2000) Assessment Guidelines For Developing a Multiculturally competent Service system. <https://portal.ct.gov/-/media/DMHAS/QMA/guidelinespdf.pdf>

35

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Original educators scale of student diversity

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 50

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures several groups of competencies of educators: cultural competency, multicultural education, culturally, responsive pedagogy and critical race theory.

REFERENCE: Patel, R. (2018). Measuring cultural competency in educators: The educators scale of student diversity (Doctoral dissertation). Seattle Pacific University.

36

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Program quality measurement tool – PQMT

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: culture

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 44

DESCRIPTION: The tool serves to evaluate the educational programming provided to students with severe disabilities against best practice indicators, identify programmatic strengths and needs, and assess improvements in educational service delivery over time. Items are organized into three sections: local education agency, school building, and student.

REFERENCE: Cushing, L., & Clark, L. M. (2002). Program Quality Measurement Tool. (Available from the Department of Special Education, Peabody College, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN.)

37

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Self-assessment checklist for personnel providing services and supports in early intervention and early childhood settings

TYPE: 3-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 49

DESCRIPTION: The instrument measures cultural and linguistic competencies by focusing on physical environment, materials and resources; communication styles and values and attitudes.

REFERENCE: Goode (2009). Promoting cultural & linguistic competency. National Centre for Cultural Competence. <https://www.sophe.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/ChecklistEIEC.pdf>

38

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Quality scale of Inclusive education development - Short form

TYPE: 4-point scale

AREA: culture, climate, competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 25

DESCRIPTION: The instrument measures the quality of inclusive education by focusing on: students with individual needs; inclusive teaching; interdisciplinary cooperation within the professional teams in school; school concept and school life, external support and communal networking.

REFERENCE: Schurig, M., Weiß, S., Kiel, E., Heimlich, U., & Gebhardt, M. (2020). Assessment of the quality of inclusive educations A short form of the quality scale of inclusive education development (QU! SS)–reliability, factorial structure and measurement invariance. International Journal of Inclusive Education, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1862405>

39

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Reflective ability

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: all three sectors

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 23

DESCRIPTION: The instrument measures the reflective ability which encompasses self-reflection, empathetic reflection and reflective communication.

REFERENCE: Aukes, L. C., Geertsma, J., Cohen-Schotanus, J., Zwierstra, R. P., & Slaets, J. P. (2007). The development of a scale to measure personal reflection in medical practice and education. *Medical teacher*, 29(2-3), 177-182.

40

ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Staff cultural competence self-assessment

TYPE: 3-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 30

DESCRIPTION: The scale focuses on educators competencies by measuring: physical environment, material and resources, communication, values and attitudes.

REFERENCE: Minneapolis Public Educations. Positive Education Climate Tool Kit. Available at: <https://guide.swifteducations.org/sites/default/files/documents/Cultural%20Competence%20and%20Equity%20-%20Educational%20%26%20Cultural%20Services.pdf>

41

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Teacher multicultural attitude survey

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 20

DESCRIPTION: The scale is focused on: teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism; emphasis of the educational system on multiculturalism and satisfaction from teaching in multicultural classrooms.

REFERENCE: Ponterotito, J. G., Baluch, S., Greig, T., & Rivera, L. (1998). Development and initial score validation of the teacher multicultural attitude survey. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 58(6), 1002-1016. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164498058006009>

42

ASSESSMENT TOOL:

Teaching in urban educations scale

TYPE: scale ("true", "false" or "don't know")

AREA: competencies

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults

No. of items: 91

DESCRIPTION: The scale measures competencies and knowledge in urban teaching and diversity with subscales referring to: teachers as professionals, families and community, emancipatory pedagogy, cultural knowledge, systemic analysis, classroom environment, student experience and importance of cultural knowledge.

REFERENCE: Swartz, E., & Bakari, R. (2005). Development of the teaching in urban educations scale. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21(7), 829-841.

43 ASSESSMENT TOOL:
Themis inclusion tool

TYPE: 5-point scale

AREA: culture, climate

SECTOR: education

TARGET GROUP: adults, young people

No. of items: 65

DESCRIPTION: This is a scale designed for teachers to reflect on the response to the diversity of students in schools. It focuses on context (in school and community), resources (personal, institutional, local) and processes (presence, participation, achievement).

REFERENCE: Azorín, C., & Ainscow, M. (2020). Guiding educators on their journey towards inclusion. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(1), 58-76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1450900>.

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Appendix

Table 1.
List of assessment tools

	Assessment tool	Culture	Climate	Competencies
1.	Administrator Cultural Competence Self-Assessment (Mineapolis Public Education)			✓
2.	Adults Tolerance Questionnaire (Blitz et al., 2020)		✓	
3.	Adults' perception of cultural competence (Leighton, 2010)			✓
4.	Assessment of cultural competences (AUCD Multicultural Council, 2004)	✓	✓	✓
5.	California Brief Multicultural Competence Scale (Gamst et al., 2004)			✓
6.	Color-Blind Racial Attitudes Scale (CoBRAS) (Neville et al., 2000)			✓
7.	Core cultural competencies (Stone & Rennekamp, 2004)			✓
8.	Critical Cultural Competence in Social Work Supervision (Lusk et al., 2017)			✓
9.	Cultural and Linguistic Competence Policy Assessment (Assessment, L. C. P.)	✓	✓	✓
10.	Cultural competence self-assessment (Andrulis et al., 2004)	✓	✓	✓
11.	Cultural Competence Self-assessment Checklist (Diversity Committee, 2018)			✓
12.	Cultural Competence Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Mason, 1995)			✓
13.	Cultural proficiency continuum Q-Sort (Cormier, 2021)			✓
14.	Diversity Climate Scale (Yeats, 2018)		✓	
15.	Diversity Management Questionnaire (Pitts, 2009)			✓

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16.	Diversity Perceptions Scale (Mor Barak et al., 1998)		✓	✓
17.	Education climate for diversity - Secondary scale (Byrd, 2019)		✓	
18.	Education climate survey (staff) (Ramsey et al., 2016)		✓	
19.	Education climate survey (young people in grade 3 to 5) (Ramsey et al., 2016)		✓	
20.	Education-wide cultural competence observation checklist (Bustamante & Nelson, 2007)	✓	✓	
21.	Ethnic-Sensitive Inventory (Ho, 1990)			✓
22.	Exploring and Assessing Intercultural Competence (Fantini, 2007)			✓
23.	Inclusive Leadership in Educations - LEI-Q questionnaire (Crisol Moya et al., 2020)			✓
24.	Index for Inclusion (Booth et al., 2002)	✓	✓	
25.	Intercultural Adjustment Potential Scale (Matsumoto et al., 2001)			✓
26.	Intercultural Sensitivity Inventory (McMurray, 2007)			✓
27.	Intercultural sensitivity scale (Hammer et al., 2003)			✓
28.	Miville-Guzman Universality-Diversity Scale (Kegel & DeBlaere, 2014)	✓		
29.	Mor Barak Inclusion-Exclusion Scale (Yeats, 2018)	✓	✓	
30.	Multicultural Awareness Knowledge and Skills Survey (D'Andrea et al., 1991)			✓
31.	Multicultural Competency Checklist (Ponterotto et al., 1995)	✓		
32.	Multicultural Counseling Inventory (Sodówsky, 1996)			✓
33.	Multicultural Personality Questionnaire (Van Der Zee & Van Oudenhoven, 2000)			✓

34.	Multiculturally Competent Service System Assessment Guide (The Connecticut Department of Mental Health and Addiction Services Office of Multicultural Affairs, 2000)	✓	✓	✓
35.	Original Educators Scale of Student Diversity (Patel, 2018)			✓
36.	Program Quality Measurement Tool (PQMT) (Cushing & Clark, 2002)	✓		
37.	Self-Assessment Checklist for Personnel Providing Services and Supports In Early Intervention and Early Childhood Settings (Goode, 2009)			✓
38.	Quality Scale of Inclusive education development - Short form (Schurig et al., 2020)	✓	✓	✓
39.	Reflective ability (Aukes et al., 2007)			✓
40.	Staff Cultural Competence Self-Assessment (Mineapolis Public Education)			✓
41.	Teacher multicultural attitude survey (Ponterotito et al., 1998)			✓
42.	Teaching in urban educations scale (Swartz & Bakari, 2005)			✓
43.	Themis inclusion tool (Azorin & Ainscow, 2020)	✓	✓	

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